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RIO OLYMPICS: TORCH OF SHOWCASING EXCELLENCE & COMMITMENT

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Abstract

Ensnconced in the luxury of our drawing rooms it is too difficult to imagine the hard work, passion, dedicated never dying spirit of excellence. Developing societies often overlook the significance of sports as they are plagued with daunting social, political and economic challenges. Olympic games are considered the world's foremost sports competition with more than 200 nations participating. The game has grown so much that nearly every nation is now represented. The game also constitutes an opportunity for the host city and country to showcase themselves to the world.

Key words: *Leadership, commitment, humanity, skills*

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Leadership, like coaching, is fighting for the hearts

And soul of men and getting them to believe in you

Eddie Robinson, legendry football coach

Introduction:

Sports since ages have been about competition and winning, team spirit, learning about other cultures. In a game we fight yet we can be friends. Sports have always been known for bringing people together in a pleasant and passionate setting. Olympics aim to promote peace and unity within the international community through the medium of sports. It also shows the whole world human side of nations. The Olympic spirit is best expressed in the Olympic creed: "The most

important thing in the Olympic game is not to win but to take part, just as the most important thing in life is not the triumph but the struggle. The essential thing is not to have conquered but to have fought well.”

The spirit of Olympics :

As Rio beckons, it is perhaps the perfect time to celebrate the spirit of Olympics. The Olympic motto is the Hendiatis Citius, Altius, Fortius which are further Latin words for Faster, Higher, Stronger. The motto for Olympics was proposed by ‘Pierre de Coubertin and according to him these three words represented a program of moral beauty. He proposed these three words upon the creation of International Olympic Committee in 1894. The motto was finally introduced in 124at the Olympic games in Paris in 1924. Also introduced by Courbertin is another informal but well known motto is “The more important thing is not to win but to take part.”

Further the emblem chosen to illustrate and represent the world congress of 1914: five intertwined rings in different colours- blue, yellow, black, green and red- are placed on white fields of paper. These five rings represent five parts of the world which now are won over to Olympism and willing to accept healthy competition, Africa, Asia, America, Europe and Oceania. The symbol was originally designed in 1912 by Baron Pierre de Coubertin, co-founder of the modern Olympic games. This design is symbolic; the five colours are those that appear on at least one of all national flags of the world at the present time united by Olympism. The Olympic medals awarded to winners are another symbol associated with the Olympic games.

Background:

From 1928 until 2000, the obverse side of the medals contained an image of Nike, the traditional goddess of victory, holding a palm min her left hand and a winners crown in her right. In 2004 the obverse side of the medal was changed to make more explicit reference to the Greek character of the games. In this design the goddess Nike flies into the Panathenic stadium, reflecting the renewal of the games.

Also Olympic diplomas are given to competitors placing fourth, fifth and sixth since 1949, and to competitors placing seventh and eighth since 1981. The Olympic Hymn officially known as the Olympic anthem is played when the Olympic flag is raised.

I always turn to sports page first,

which records people's accomplishments.

The front page has nothing but man's failures.

Earl Warren, American jurist

As the dust has just started to rise across the stadium of Olympics with the newspapers replete with stories of thousands thronging the venue Indians are having their share of special moments by witnessing gymnast Dipa Kirmakar creating history by making it to the finals of the event. Kirmakar eighth in the individual vault finals after successfully pulling off the dangerous "Produnova" stunt and securing 14.850 points.

In the first ever modern Olympic games just 241 men from 14 countries competed in 1896. Those inaugural games of the Olympiad held in Athens were not sophisticated as they are now. In 1896 swimming competitions were held out in open sea, such were those times. Yachting event was scheduled but had to be cancelled as no one thought to show up with boats in the first

Olympiad.

The Olympic games now feature more than 27,000 elite athletes from more than 200 countries competing in 28 sports. Every four years the world assembles, in a specific distinguished city for the celebration of every nation's outstanding sportspersons. The ones with passion, spark and spirit of breaking barriers, transcending limits, reaching new heights of excellence make it for the Olympics.

*"Gold medals aren't really made of gold. They're made of sweat,
determination and a hard-to-find alloy called guts."*

Dan Gable, 1972 gold medal winner in wrestling

Every four years the world witnesses supreme sense of unity, shattering the boundaries of country, time, space, springing in the cradle of humanity.

There can't be a better example to show as to how world can be united through the medium of sports. The medal's, five rings, flags waving in air making every country man proud, the cheering crowd, the carrying of torch, the wonder and awe is what makes Olympics for a common man. An emotional experience is what this event is all about both for the sports person and the country men.

Conclusion:

Therefore it can be said that goal of the Olympic movement is to contribute to build a peaceful and better world by educating the youth through practicing sports by educating youth. Also making the youth understand the true spirit of Olympics which requires mutual understanding, solidarity and fair play. And finally winning is not just about medals, certificates and trophies rather it's about improving skills, gaining personal best and giving 100%, challenging ones own limits. Ultimately winning should be about continuous learning, process of improvement and raising the bars. Concept of Olympism are not merely about sports alone; they are a collection of values and prescribed practices about humanity and its treatment Let us wish Rio 2016 and the Indian contingent all the success.

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